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International Branding of Higher Education Institutions towards World-Class Universities: Literature Study in 2017- 2022

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Abstract

Struggles initiated to accomplish the target of higher education institutions as World-Class Universities required the support of an international branding strategy. Brand positioning that fits the target enables the higher education institution to be a public "Top of Mind". Higher education institutions must develop and improve the standard of branding. Thus, higher education institutions can handle the rising competition in the educational field, not only at the local and national levels but also at the international level. The researchers conducted a qualitative study with a literature study based on the Publish or Perish program to discover research trends on international branding of the higher education institution to achieve and maintain the title of World-Class University. The search results for journal publications on Google Scholar in 2017-2022 were subsequently processed using the Vos Viewer program to generate data visualizations that could elaborate on the development of research trends related to the abovementioned topic. The 89 most relevant terms were obtained and divided into six clusters. The most dominant research topic, especially in 2020, was the impact of Covid-19, which caused changes in various fields. Specifically, the teaching system, which was initially conducted offline, had changed to become more online in the education sector. "Covid" was also the word that arose the most in the results of this literature study.

Keywords: Literature Study, International Branding, Higher Education Institutions, World-Class Universities

1. Introduction

Higher education institutions must have high academic and non-academic quality in the global era. Furthermore, higher education institutions can handle the rising competition in the educational field, not only at the local and national levels but also at the international level. For this reason, higher education institutions must correspond to international performance assessment standards regarding the results of the Quacquarelli Symonds-World University Rankings (QS-WUR), Times Higher Education (THE), Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU), or Webometrics. Furthermore, one of the indicators is the internationalization of the higher education institution.

The 2022 QS WUR ranking places Universitas Gadjah Mada (UGM) in 254th place worldwide and first out of 16 participating Indonesian universities. At the beginning of each year, UGM Public Relations determines one big theme as material for publication exposure. The theme is determined through in-depth research on global societal issues, and UGM contributes to solving them. Reporting the contributions in the mass media and social media is part of UGM's branding efforts to become "Top of Mind" as the best university in Indonesia at the international level (Sugiharso & Setianingrum, 2021). Brand positioning that fits the target will generate a robust memory in the public's minds. Thus, the public will refer to a particular brand if required. Higher education institutions must develop and improve the quality of good branding. Thus, higher education institutions can handle the rising competition. Stakeholders will easily forget higher education institutions that do not have excellent branding.

Social media utilization positively impacts higher education institution branding (Rutter et al., 2016) (Momen et al., 2020) (Nguyen et al., 2021). Based on data from the Global Overview Report 2022, 62.5% of the world's population are active internet users. The trend of students using social media to participate in the Community Field Project has also generally improved higher education institution branding (Cahya et al., 2022). The more frequently this branding is accomplished, the more it will be attached to the higher education institution, and the public will realize and recognize it more. One of the strategies implemented by Telkom University towards A World-Class University is to brand the I-Gracias application, which is an international standard distance learning system that is beneficial in the IT field (Muhardiawan et al., 2016). It is inevitably conducted because reputation and branding are essential elements in higher education institution management practices (Aula & Tienari, 2011), especially for World-Class Universities. Branding activities are crucial because in order to remain competitive, university traditions are no longer the only reason (Šerić, 2017), but instead focus more on excellence.

The concept of branding at higher education institutions can provide a good reputation both in terms of services and facilities offered to prospective students (Kusumah & Yusuf, 2020). In addition, branding is also an element that supports the improvement of the quality of the international student recruitment process succession since the promotion and marketing stages (Al-Thagafi et al., 2020)(Wang & Crawford, 2021)(Kisiołek et al., 2021)(Mohamad Saleh et al., 2022). Regarding the purpose of attracting more interest from international students, higher education institution branding must also consist of the national characteristics, values, and qualities of the country (Sataøen, 2019).

Branding combines various elements such as names, terms, symbols, and designs to differentiate the products and services from competitors (Kotler et al., 2008). People can recognize what a brand product offers by developing the correct perception of public awareness. In higher education institutions, branding is a set of communication activities to build and enlarge a brand. Branding development is one of the efforts to build a higher education institution's image based on reputation and achievement (Purwowidodo & Yasin, 2021). A strong brand will aid in developing a higher education institution identity in the community to improve relations with stakeholders (Elving et al., 2015).

In discovering research trends on international branding of higher education institutions to achieve and maintain the title of World-Class University, the researchers conducted a study using literature studies.

2. Method

This article was qualitative research using the Publish or Perish program-based literature study method, accessed on January 1, 2023. Data were obtained from searching journal publications on Google Scholar using a 6-year database from 2017-2022 to accomplish the latest research trends that identify keywords: international branding AND higher education institution AND world class university.

Figure 1. Search results for journal publications based on the Publish or Perish program

Over six years, there were 998 journals related to the keywords "international branding AND higher education institution AND world-class university", which had been cited 234527 times. The search results were subsequently processed using Vos Viewer program to create data visualizations that could elaborate on the development of research trends (Ranjbar-Sahraei & Negenborn, 2017) related to international branding of higher education institutions to achieve and maintain the title of World-Class University. The appropriate settings were completed in the VosViewer program. Thus, the visualized data could be improved.

Figure 2: The minimum threshold for the appearance of the terms to use

Systematically, the program regulated the threshold for the appearance of a term to be 10. It indicates that a term to use in this research must appear at least ten times in an article. The research data found 5735 terms with a certain number of repetitions, but only 148 fulfilled the threshold.

The subsequent stage was to determine the terms to use by setting the percentage of the most relevant terms. In this study, the program's default settings specified the 89 most relevant terms to include.

Figure 3: The number of terms to be selected in the study

Among the 89 most relevant terms, several conjunctions and meaningless words appeared. However, all terms were still included in the visualization of the research map to provide a complete picture of the studies conducted. The journal search used the Publish or Perish program, and the results of which were visualized using the Vos Viewer. It can be a reference to discover the mapping of research areas that have not received much attention. It is beneficial for researchers to discover novelty and research gaps, as well as variables that will probably be applied for further research; accordingly, there are developments, and new results are discovered (Rofik et al., 2022).

3. Results

Based on search results on Google Scholar in 2017-2022 using the keywords: international branding AND higher education institution AND world-class university, the number of journals published per year is obtained as follows:

Table 1: Number of journals each year

Year	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Amount	325	244	141	221	50	17
Percentage	32.57 %	24.45 %	14.13 %	22.14 %	5.01 %	1.70 %

Graph 1: Number of journals each year

The number of research journals on this topic decreased from 2017 to 2019 but increased in 2020 and declined sharply again in 2021 and 2022. From the search results in Figure 1, there are 23 journals cited more than 1000 times as follows:

Table 2: Journals cited more than 1000 times

No	Number of citations	Writer	Title	Journal	Year
1	7533	Paul A. Harris, Robert Taylor, Brenda L. Minor, Veida Elliott, Michelle Fernandez,	The REDCap consortium: Building an international community of software platform partners	Journal of Biomedical Informatics	2019
2	5975	Maria Nicola, Zaid Alsafi, Catrin Sohrabi, Ahmed Kerwan, Ahmed Al-Jabir,	The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19): A review	International Journal of Surgery	2020
3	4331	Shivangi Dhawan	Online learning: A panacea in the time of COVID-19 crisis	Journal of educational technology systems	2020
4	4088	Stefan Gössling, Daniel Scott, C. Michael Hall	Pandemics, tourism and global change: a rapid assessment of COVID-19	Journal of sustainable tourism	2020
5	3395	Paul McCrory, Willem Meeuwisse, Jiri Dvorak, Mark Aubry, Julian Bailes	Consensus statement on concussion in sport—the 5th international conference on concussion in sport held in Berlin, October 2016	British journal of sports Med	2017
6	2073	Joseph Crawford, Kerrynt Butler-Henderson, Jurgen Rudolph, Bashar Malkawi, Matt Glowatz	COVID-19: 20 countries' higher education institution intra-period digital pedagogy responses	Journal of Applied Learning & Teaching	2020
7	2006	Changwon Son, Sudeep Hegde, Alec Smith, Xiaomei Wang, Farzan Sasangohar	Effects of COVID-19 on college students' mental health in the United States: Interview survey study	Journal of medical Internet Research	2020
8	1826	Lokanath Mishra, Tushar Gupta, Abha Shree	Online teaching-learning in higher education institution during the lockdown period of COVID-19 pandemic	International Journal of Educational Research Open	2020
9	1635	Noah C Peeri, Nistha Shrestha, Md Siddikur Rahman, Rafdzah Zaki, Zhengqi Tan	The SARS, MERS and novel coronavirus (COVID-19) epidemics, the newest and biggest global health threats: what lessons have we learned?	International journal of Epidemiology	2020
10	1626	Mohammed Eslam, Philip N. Newsome, Shiv K. Sarin, Quentin M. Anstee, Giovanni Targher	A new definition for metabolic dysfunction-associated fatty liver disease: An international expert consensus statement	Journal of Hepatology	2020
11	1450	Jagdish Sheth	Impact of Covid-19 on consumer behavior: Will the old habits return or die?	Journal of business research	2020
12	1318	Hongwei He, Lloyd Harris	The impact of Covid-19 pandemic on corporate social responsibility and marketing philosophy	Journal of business research	2020
13	1300	Randy P. Auerbach, Phillipe Mortier, Ronny Bruffaerts, Jordi Alonso, Corina Benjet,	WHO World Mental Health Surveys International College Student Project: Prevalence and distribution of mental disorders.	Journal of abnormal Psychology	2018

14	1245	Stephen L. Vargo, Robert F. Lusch	Service-dominant logic 2025	International Journal of Research in Marketing	2017
15	1184	Neal I. Lindeman, Philip T. Cagle, Dara L. Aisner, Maria E. Arcila, Mary Beth Beasley,	Updated Molecular testing guidelines for the selection of lung cancer patients for treatment with targeted tyrosine kinase inhibitors	Journal of Thoracic Oncology	2018
16	1118	Mucahid Mustafa Saritas, Ali Yasar	Performance analysis of ANN and Naive Bayes classification algorithm for data classification	International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering	2019
17	1104	Johanes König, Daniela J. Jäger-Biela, Nina Glutsch	Adapting to online teaching during COVID-19 school closure: teacher education and teacher competence effects among early career teachers in Germany	European Journal of Teacher Education	2020
18	1051	Oberiri D. Apuke	Quantitative research methods: A synopsis approach	Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review	2017
19	1041	Latania K. Logan, Robert A. Weinstein	The epidemiology of carbapenem- resistant Enterobacteriaceae: the impact and evolution of a global menace	The Journal of infectious diseases	2017
20	1030	Jochen Wirtz, Paul G. Patterson, Werner H. Kunz, Thorsten Gruber, Vinh Nhat Lu,	Brave new world: service robots in the frontline	Journal of Service Management	2018
21	1024	Morteza Ghobakhloo	The future of manufacturing industry: a strategic roadmap toward Industry 4.0	Journal of manufacturing technology management	2018
22	1017	A. Patricia Aguilera- Hermida	College students' use and acceptance of emergency online learning due to COVID-19	International Journal of Educational Research Open	2020
23	1012	Mansureh Kebritchi, Angie Lipschuetz, Lilia Santiago	Issues and challenges for teaching successful online courses in higher education institution: A literature review	Journal of Educational Technology Systems	2017

Based on table 2, it appears that health topics, especially those related to the COVID-19 pandemic, were very dominant and were widely cited in 2020. It definitely occurred due to the coronavirus's appearance toward the end of 2019 and the numerous changes it has brought about in various fields. Specifically, in the education sector, the teaching system, which was initially conducted offline, has changed to become more online. Learning is not restricted by time or space using an online system. The positive impact of this change on higher education institution branding is the ease and speed of promoting programs and disseminating information that can create a positive reputation by utilizing digital technology, which proliferates during the pandemic.

The journal data in Figure 1, which was subsequently processed using the Vos Viewer, discovered 2391 author names. The program default sets 1000 of them as having the greatest total link strength. Link strength is not related to the number of connections with other authors. However, the ranking criteria for journal are due to where articles are published and the number of cited articles.

Figure 4: The number of selected authors for the study

Authors who have a total link strength of more than six are:

Selected	Author	Documents	Total link strength
☒	zhang, c	2	11
☒	filho, w leal	4	9
☒	he, y	2	8
☒	paul, j	8	7
☒	hall, cm	4	7
☒	han, h	3	7
☒	kim, s	2	7
☒	leong, c	2	7

Figure 5: Authors who have a total link strength of more than six

Even though Chaiyun Zhang only wrote two journals with topics related to this research keyword, he has the greatest total link strength because his articles are published in top-ranked journals, and the number of articles cited is enormous. In contrast, the following authors have published in more than three journals as follows:

Selected	Author	Documents	Total link strength
☒	paul, j	8	7
☒	filho, w leal	4	9
☒	hall, cm	4	7
☒	bond, m	4	5
☒	han, h	3	7
☒	bedenlier, s	3	4
☒	marin, vi	3	4
☒	kumar, v	3	3

Figure 6: Authors who wrote in more than three journals

The details of the data are as follows:

Table 3: Details of data on authors who wrote more than three journals

No	Writer	Title	Journal	Year
a. Justin Paul: eight documents, seven total link strength				
a.1	Ajay Kumara, Justin Paul, Anandakuttan B. Unnithane	'Masstige' marketing: A review, synthesis and research agenda	Journal of Business Research	2020
a.2	Alexander Rosado-Serrano, Justin Paul, Desislava Dikovac	International franchising: A literature review and research agenda	Journal of Business Research	2018
a.3	Justin Paul	Masstige model and measure for brand management	European Management Journal	2019
a.4	Justin Paul	Marketing in emerging markets: a review, theoretical synthesis and extension	International Journal of Emerging Markets	2020

a.5	Justin Paul	Toward a 'masstige' theory and strategy for marketing	European J. International Management	2018
a.6	Justin Paul , Erick Mas	Toward a 7-P framework for international marketing	Journal of Strategic Marketing	2020
a.7	Justin Paul , Weng Marc Lim , Aron O'Cass , Andy Wei Hao , Stefano Bresciani	Scientific procedures and rationales for systematic literature reviews (SPAR-4-SLR)	International Journal of Consumer Studies	2021
a.8	Vikas Arya , Justin Paul , Deepa Sethi	Like it or not! Brand communication on social networking sites triggers consumer-based brand equity	International Journal of Consumer Studies	2021
b. Walter Leal Filho: four documents, nine total link strength				
b. 1	Walter Leal Filho , Chris Shiel, Arminda Paço, Mark Mifsud, Lucas Veiga Avila,....	Sustainable Development Goals and sustainability teaching at universities: Falling behind or getting ahead of the pack?	Journal of cleaner production	2019
b.2	Walter Leal Filho , Edward A. Morgan, Eric S. Godoy, Ulisses M. Azeiteiro, Paula Bacelar-Nicolau,	Implementing climate change research at universities: Barriers, potential and actions	Journal of cleaner production	2018
b.3	W. Leal Filho , S. Raath, B. Lazzarini, VR Vargas, L. de Souza,....	The role of transformation in learning and education for sustainability	Journal of cleaner production	2018
b.4	Walter Leal Filho , Yen-Chun Jim Wu, Luciana Londero Brandli, Lucas Veiga Avila, Ulisses Miranda Azeiteiro,...	Identifying and overcoming obstacles to the implementation of sustainable development at universities	Journal of Integrative Environmental Sciences	2017
c. C. Michael Hall: four documents, seven total link strength				
c. 1	Bailey Ashton Adie , C. Michael Hall	Who visits World Heritage? A comparative analysis of three cultural sites	Journal of Heritage Tourism	2017
c. 2	Bailey Ashton Adie , C. Michael Hall , Girish Prayag	World Heritage as a placebo brand: A comparative analysis of three sites and marketing implications	Journal of Sustainable Tourism	2018
c. 3	Ove Oklevik , Stefan Gössling , C. Michael Hall , Jens Kristian Steen Jacobsen , Ivar Petter Grotte , Scott McCabe	Overtourism, optimization, and destination performance indicators: A case study of activities in Fjord Norway	Journal of Sustainable Tourism	2019
c. 4	Stefan Gössling , Daniel Scott , C. Michael Hall	Pandemics, tourism and global change: a rapid assessment of COVID-19	Journal of sustainable tourism	2020
d. Melissa Bond: four documents, five total link strength				
d. 1	Melissa Bond , Katja Buntins, Svenja Bedenlier, Olaf Zawacki-Richter, and Michael Kerres	Mapping research in student engagement and educational technology in higher education institution: A systematic evidence map	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher education institution	2020
d.2	Melissa Bond , Olaf Zawacki-Richter, Mark Nichols	Revisiting five decades of educational technology research: A content and authorship analysis of the British Journal of Educational Technology	British Journal of Educational Technology	2019
d.3	Melissa Bond , Svenja Bedenlier, Victoria I. Marín, Marion Händel	Emergency remote teaching in higher education institution: Mapping the first global online semester	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher education institution	2021

d.4	Melissa Bond, Victoria I. Marín, Carina Dolch, Svenja Bedenlier and Olaf Zawacki-Richter	Digital transformation in German higher education institution: student and teacher perceptions and usage of digital media	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher education institution	2018
e. Heesup Han: three documents, seven total link strength				
e. 1	HakJun Song, JunHui Wang, Heesup Han,	Effect of image, satisfaction, trust, love, and respect on loyalty formation for name-brand coffee shops	International Journal of Hospitality Management	2019
e.2	Amr Al-Ansi, Hossein GT Olya, Heesup Han	Effect of general risk on trust, satisfaction, and recommendation intention for halal food	International Journal of Hospitality Management	2019
e.4	Seoyoung Kim, Sunny Ham, Hyeyoung Moon, Bee-Lia Chua, Heesup Han,	Experience, brand prestige, perceived value (functional, hedonic, social, and financial), and loyalty among GROCERANT customers	International Journal of Hospitality Management	2019
f. Svenja Bedenlier: three documents, four total link strength				
f. 1	Svenja Bedenlier, Yasar Kondakci , Olaf Zawacki-Richter	Two Decades of Research Into the Internationalization of Higher education institution: Major Themes in the Journal of Studies in International Education (1997-2016)	Journal of Studies in International Education	2018
f. 2	Melissa Bond, Svenja Bedenlier, Victoria I. Marín, Marion Händel	Emergency remote teaching in higher education institution: Mapping the first global online semester	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher education institution	2021
f.3	Melissa Bond, Katja Buntins, Svenja Bedenlier, Olaf Zawacki-Richter, Michael Kerres	Mapping research in student engagement and educational technology in higher education institution: A systematic evidence map	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher education institution	2020
g. Victoria I. Marín: three documents, four total link strength				
g. 1	Olaf Zawacki-Richter, Victoria I. Marín , Melissa Bond, Franziska Gouverneur	Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education institution – where are the educators?	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher	2019
g. 2	Melissa Bond, Victoria I. Marín , Carina Dolch, Svenja Bedenlier, Olaf Zawacki-Richter	Digital transformation in German higher education institution: student and teacher perceptions and usage of digital media	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher education institution	2018
g. 3	Melissa Bond, Svenja Bedenlier, Victoria I. Marín , and Marion Händel	Emergency remote teaching in higher education institution: Mapping the first global online semester	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher education institution	2021
h. Vikas Kumar: three documents, three total link strength				
h. 1	Jitendra Singh, Vikas Kumar, Darvinder Kumar	Combating the Pandemic With ICT-Based Learning Tools and Applications: A Case of Indian Higher education institution	International Journal of Virtual and Personal Learning Environments	2022
h. 2	Shaphali Gupta, Anita Pansari, V. Kumar	Global customer engagement	Journal of International Marketing	2018
h. 3	V Kumar	Transformative marketing: The next 20 years	Journal of Marketing	2018

Table 3 shows the specifications of the research topic interests of each researcher. Regarding research focusing on international branding of higher education institutions to achieve and maintain the title of World-Class University,

authors who deserve to be references are Walter Leal Filho, Melissa Bond, Svenja Bedenlier, and Victoria I. Marín. The combination of link strength and the number of journals generates a network map visualization of 1000 authors as follows:

Figure 7: Visualization of the author's network

The circle of names that are light in colour indicates authors with a great total link strength or numerous journals. Data processing of the 89 most relevant terms in 998 journals accessed through Google Scholar in the period 2017-2022 related to the keywords "international branding AND higher education institution AND world class university", generated a network map visualization using the Vos Viewer as follows:

Figure 8: Network visualization

In Figure 8, terms are represented by labels, whose size is determined by the frequency of appearance in the title and abstract. The more frequently the term appeared, the greater the label size was. The terms are classified according to the respective field categories that correlate with the main topic. Each cluster represents a special sub-discussion regarding the topic of international branding of higher education institutions to achieve and maintain the title of World-Class Universities. Based on Figure 8, it appears that there are six clusters with the following details:

Table 4: Clustering of relevant terms in the study based on the visualization map

Cluster /Color	Term	Number of Terms
1 / Red	addition, article, creativity, difference, evidence, example, field, framework, future, global brand, india, industry, innovation, international marketing, journal, literature, management, market, marketing, meta analysis, part, relationship, study design, systematic review, theory	25

2 / Green	activity, critical thinking skill, cross sectional design , high school, high school student, indonesia, junior high school, model, order, participant, problem, project, researcher, sample, science, skill, stem	19
3 / Blue	adoption, case, china, e learning, heis, international student, learner, malaysia, online learning, online teaching, paper, patient, social medium, strategy, survey	15
4 / Yellow	blended learning, child, covid, crisis, educator, gender, implication, online, online education, pandemic, physical activity, university student, year	13
5 / Purple	barrier, case study, evaluation, importance, issue, person, sustainability, sustainable development, tertiary education, transition	10
6 / Light blue	brand, consumer, effectiveness, policy, product, service, value	7

The first cluster's categorization shows a close relationship between global brands and creativity, difference, and innovation. Product/service differentiation and innovation, accompanied by the proper promotion strategy, will support the creation of positive branding (Paul, 2019). Concerning university branding, based on Figure 9 there is no visible network between global brands and HEIs (Higher education institution's) or students, meaning that this topic has not been or is still rarely researched.

Figure 9: Network visualization of the term “global brand”

In the second cluster, the terms appear as follows: critical thinking skills, cross-sectional design, and skills closely related to high school students. Research related to higher education institutions in the early period of the pandemic was more related to changes/modifications/exploration of learning systems, their impact on students' skills, and how they perceived these changes. Most of the research was conducted descriptively and cross-sectionally with a focus on the fields of Health, Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math (STEM) (Bond et al., 2021).

The third cluster visualizes that branding is inseparable from digitizing information. Thus, the terms appeared as follows: e learning, online teaching, and social medium. Establishing a brand image in the minds of consumers begins with creating brand love and respect, which will significantly lead to brand loyalty. For this reason, management must strengthen publications related to brand image through advertisements and information media to deepen customer impressions and simultaneously attract increasing enthusiasts (Song et al., 2019). If people focus on the term HEI, the visualization in Figure 10 shows that HEI already has a relationship with the brand, but the distance is far away. Most of the HEI research is still related to teaching and learning. Thus, there are still various new opportunities for research on higher education institution brands.

Figure 10: Network visualization of the term “HEIs”

The fourth cluster is a study group related to the crisis that appeared as a result of the pandemic due to the spread of Covid, which generated restrictions on physical activity. Accordingly, the blended learning method was applied. In contrast, offline learning declined, and online learning increased. Various online educational portals emerged at that time, such as SWAYAM and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC) platform highly popular in India (Singh et al., 2022).

The fifth cluster revealed the following terms: evaluation, importance, issue, sustainability, sustainable development, higher education institution, and transition. The Sustainable Development Goals are targets that the entire world community desires to achieve; accordingly, higher education institutions should also be involved in teaching and catalyzing student involvement (Filho et al., 2019).

The sixth cluster shows that the combination of product and service quality is the most effective brand instrument to attract consumer interest. Business success combines product/service quality with a unique and memorable consumer experience as purchasing/using the product. The distinctive experience grants clients a sense of brand prestige, strengthening customer loyalty (Kim et al., 2019).

The second visualization generated by the Vos Viewer program is mapping research trends by year category, as shown in Figure 11. Dark colours represent terms that became research trends in previous years. In comparison, lighter colours represent research trends in recent years. In 2017-2019, the research trend in the education sector was dominated by learning systems focused on STEM. Meanwhile, the branding topic is more related to the industrial sector, and branding also functions as part of marketing efforts to reach consumers. As previously discussed, the trend of research in 2020-2022 is more related to the impact of the Covid pandemic, especially in higher education institution teaching, which has changed to an online-based system.

Figure 11: Overlay Visualization

The Vos Viewer program also generates a visualization map that explains the density of keywords/terms, which can further elaborate word groupings. This third map describes the most widely discussed terms related to the international branding of higher education institutions to achieve and maintain the title of World-Class University. The frequently appearing terms have the thickest density or most vigorous color intensity, as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Density visualization

Quantitatively, the terms that appear most often are as follows:

Table 5: Appearance of terms

No	Term	Appearance
1.	Covid	149
2.	High school	112
3.	Brand	90
4.	Pandemic	89
5.	Model	84
6.	Marketing	74
7.	Strategy	59
8.	Year	45
9.	Activity	42
10.	High school student	35
11.	Skills	35
12.	Paper	33
13.	Frameworks	31
14.	Systematic review	31
15.	University student	30
16.	Management	30

The frequent appearance of a term is not equivalent to its relevance level due to the topic of international higher education institution branding to achieve and maintain the title of World-Class University. Of the 89 terms generated from a Publish or Perish search and subsequently processed using the Vos Viewer, 34 words were found to have multiple relevant meanings, namely:

Table 6: The level of relevance of terms is more than 1.0

No	Term	Relevance
1.	Critical thinking skills	3.64
2.	Junior high school	3,22
3.	Consumer	2.74
4.	Patient	2.01
5.	Meta analysis	1.89
6.	Problem	1.81

7.	International marketing	1.75
8.	Brands	1.64
9.	Online teaching	1.62
10.	Global brand	1.59
11.	Online education	1.58
12.	Sample	1.50
13.	English	1.47
14.	Theory	1.46
15.	Learner	1.39
16.	Creativity	1.37
17.	Sustainability	1.31
18.	Experimental design	1.29
19.	Sustainable development	1.26
20.	Indonesia	1.25
21.	Evaluation	1.24
22.	Project	1.24
23.	Articles	1.23
24.	Addition	1.22
25.	Industry	1.19
26.	skills	1.19
27.	On line	1.15
28.	Cross sectional design	1.14
29.	Online learning	1.12
30.	Value	1.05
31.	Barrier	1.03
32.	Journals	1.01
33.	High school student	1.00
34.	Stem	1.00

There are 55 terms that have a relevance level of less than 1.0, with the lowest relevance at 0.28. Terms with a high level of relevance but low appearance are potential topics for further research concerning international branding of higher education institutions to achieve and maintain the title of World-Class University. These terms include Critical thinking skills, Meta analysis, International marketing, Online teaching, and Global brand.

4. Discussions

Regarding the literature study based on the Publish or Perish program, which searched for journal publications on Google Scholar in 2017-2022 using the keywords: international branding AND higher education institution AND world class university, 998 journals were obtained. Data processing with Vos Viewer determined the 89 most relevant terms that produce three types of visualization maps, as follows:

1. visuality network: there are six clusters due to grouping terms according to their respective field categories that correlate with the main topic. No relationship was found between the terms of HEI and global brand. Thus, it indicates that this topic has not been or rarely researched.
2. visuality overlay: the impact of the pandemic dominates the topic of research results, especially in 2020. Particularly in the educational field, the research focus is still related to modifying the teaching system, which was initially conducted face-to-face, to be online.
3. visuality density: several terms have a high level of relevance but low appearance. Thus, the terms potentially become future research topics.

The conclusion from this literature study is that there are still limited journal publications related to the topic of research on international branding of higher education institutions to achieve and maintain the title of World-Class University. As a practical implication, new research topics with a high level of novelty and significant research gaps will be obtained by selecting several relevant terms that rarely appear.

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